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<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/>

Nextfood - Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

Practice Abstract #15: Nextfood educational strategy, year 1

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A central part of the Nextfood project is the 12 case studies conducted in 10 countries on 3 continents. All these cases are attempting to transform their education models to align with the Nextfood approach. Not only are we trying to make the change, but we are also researching the process and the outcomes. In this document, we report on the outcomes of implementing the Nextfood educational strategy during the first year of the project. Throughout the first year, the selected cases have been engaged with initiating their case work, primarily through planning the initial steps of employing the Nextfood approach. The initial reports from carrying out the educational activities suggest that the Nextfood approach is well suited for developing students' required competences in dealing with a complex reality. However, we also observe signs that the approach may be less successful if the implementation is not performed in a comprehensive way. For the coming cycles, we expect to gain a better understanding of the necessary steps needed to successfully implement the Nextfood approach in the selected cases.

For practitioners looking to implement elements of action learning related to the Nextfood approach, we recommend to thoroughly plan the activities and to set up a system to gather reflections on the process. We have found that it is necessary to not only learn by doing, but also to reflect upon the experiences. Reflections upon how the first year of implementing the Nextfood approach has gone can be read about in this document.